

Eye Health Knowledge Assessment Among Secondary School Students in Onitsha, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: Eye health knowledge drives appropriate behaviours that are favourable to healthy vision. Evaluating the eye health knowledge of school children aids in identifying information gaps and improving knowledge on eye health education. **Objectives:** To determine the level of eye health knowledge and also the effectiveness of an eye health education intervention among secondary school students in Onitsha, Nigeria. **Methodology:** A before-and-after study design was used to assess the efficacy of eye health education among secondary school students. A questionnaire was used to assess eye health knowledge among students. The same questionnaire was re-administered after an educational intervention. The comparisons between means was done using T-test while Chi-square test was used to analyse association between categorical variables. **Results:** A total of 296 students made up of 178 (60.1%) males and 118 (39.9%) females with a mean age of 14.7 ± 1.3 years (Range 12-19 years), took part in this study. There was a fair knowledge score of 13.67 ± 3.75 (54.7%) before the educational intervention. The eye health knowledge post-intervention score improved to 19.33 ± 3.38 (77.3%), representing a good knowledge ($p = 0.05$). Students in junior secondary school had a statistically significant higher mean change in knowledge score than those in senior secondary school ($t = 2.46; p = 0.015$). There was no statistically significant difference in mean change in knowledge score between males and females ($t = 0.370, p = 0.599$). **Conclusion:** Eye health education increased the awareness and knowledge of healthy eye behaviours and good eye practices among the secondary school students. We recommend the use of posters, audio-visual displays, role plays and demonstrations in addition to lectures to enhance eye health knowledge among secondary school students.

Key words: Eye health knowledge, Students, Education, Intervention, Assessment.

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INTRODUCTION

Blindness and visual impairment are major causes of disability and its resultant socioeconomic problems in the society.¹ They place significant burden on individuals, families, and the society as a whole. The negative effects of blindness are more marked in developing countries where access to quality health care is limited by infrastructure and resources.¹ Globally, an estimated two million children are blind and another 88 million suffering from different levels of sight loss.² Visual impairment in children has a significant impact on educational outcomes, self-esteem, future socioeconomic potential and even mortality.^{3,4}

The eye health of children and adolescents is crucial to their motor, language, emotional, social and cognitive development, and achievement of their life dreams and potentials. Good knowledge of eye health will enable children to start assuming their role as stakeholders in their own eye health early. It will help drive appropriate behaviours that are favourable to their eye health. This will help ensure they maximally enjoy the benefits of good eye health through their life course. Schools present a great opportunity for impartation of eye health knowledge within comprehensive school eye health. Information learned in these formative years is important in shaping and influencing children into their adult years. Eye health information learned by children also impacts their families which is beneficial for the wider society.⁵ School health programs can play an essential role in eye health promotion, prevention, early detection and treatment of ocular problems in children. The practice of school eye health is still rudimentary in many parts of Nigeria.⁶

It is not clear how much eye health information school children are exposed to and to what extent they are retained. Evaluating the eye health knowledge of school children is important in

tailoring eye health education, promotion and preventive strategies to their needs. It will help identify gaps in knowledge for which educational interventions will be tailored. The aim of this study is to determine the level of eye health knowledge among secondary students in Onitsha, Nigeria. This study will also assess the effectiveness of an eye health education intervention on the eye health knowledge among these students.

METHODOLOGY

This was a before-and-after study design done among students of a co-educational government-owned secondary school in Onitsha North Local Government Area (LGA), Onitsha Anambra State as part of activities to mark the World Sight day 2024. A questionnaire, based on information contained in the 'Health eyes Activity Book: a healthy Teaching Book for primary schools'⁷ was developed and used for this study. A pilot study of the questionnaire was done among secondary students in another local LGA to refine and improve the quality of the questionnaire as a research instrument. ~~However, the questionnaire was not validated.~~

A self-administered pretested questionnaire was used for this study. The questionnaire consists of 5 sections, each containing 5 questions, making a total of 25 questions. It contained sociodemographic data such as age, gender and class. The questions were on eye injury, red eye/conjunctivitis, causes of blindness, spectacle and vision. The questionnaire was first administered a day before delivery of an intervention involving health talk and demonstration on eye health derived from information contained in the Healthy eyes activity book⁷ The same questionnaire was administered immediately after the educational activity to the students who had participated in the pre-intervention test.

The health talk/lecture and demonstrations were carried out by an Ophthalmologist. The eye health education held after the morning assembly and was delivered to all students of the school from the stage of the assembly ground. The duration of the eye health talk was approximately 45 minutes. It was interactive with questions and answer from both the students and ophthalmologist. The content of the eye health education include the negative impact of blindness on life such as limited interaction with environment, reduced educational and developmental attainment, social and economic problems; common causes of blindness such as cataract, glaucoma, diabetes, corneal blindness from measles; common eye problems in children such as red eyes and refractive errors were also included. Eye injuries and prevention of eye injuries in the school environment and home were also addressed in the interactive eye health talk. Also covered were the importance of correct use of spectacle and debunking myths related to spectacle use such as children are too young to wear glasses, glasses shrink the eye balls and weaken the eyes. Also covered were the common traditional eye medications and practices as well as dangers of use of traditional eye medications. Finally, things that can be done to keep the eyes healthy were taught, including keeping faces clean, eating healthy food including those rich in Vitamin A, immunization against measles, going for treatment early when there is an eye problem, getting eye check-ups, and avoiding using medicines or anything else in your eyes without advice by a competent health care provider. In the course of the interactive session, eye health posters were used to educate the students and promote better understanding. Eye health fliers summarizing the key points were distributed to each student after the eye health talk.

Eligibility criteria: inclusion criteria were students of the secondary school aged 12 years and above, who are currently enrolled in the school, have spent at least one full term and with

parental consent to participate in the study. The students whose parents withheld consent and those unwell were excluded from the study.

Sample size determination and sampling technique:

The secondary school had a total of 900 students. This was used as population of the study to calculate sample size. The minimum sample size was calculated using the Cochran formula for sample size in sampling for proportions:⁸

$$n = Z^2pq/d^2$$

n = minimum sample size

Z = the normal deviation at 95% confidence interval (1.96)

p = the proportion of eye health knowledge in a study by Karna and Singh^[5] (44%)

$$q = 1 - p$$

d = absolute error or precision (was set at 5% or 0.05)

To calculate n

$$= (1.962 \times 0.44 \times 0.56) / 0.052$$

$$= 0.9466 / 0.0025$$

$$n = 378.64 \approx 379$$

Cochran correction for a small population was applied (since sample size >5% of the population) using the following formula: ^[8]

$$nf = n / [1 + (n/N)]$$

where

nf = adjusted sample size for small population

n = minimum sample size as calculated above

N = population size

$$= 379 / 1 + (379/900)$$

$$= 379 / 1 + 0.421$$

$$= 379 / 1.421$$

$$= 266.71 \approx 267$$

Calculated minimum sample size for studying the students was 267

To accommodate for attrition, 10% of this minimum sample size was added:

$$10\% \text{ of } 267 = 26.7 \approx 27$$

$$\text{Sample Size for the study} = 267 + 27 = 294$$

Sampling technique involved stratified random sampling with proportionate allocation of sample size. Each class was taken as a stratum. The sample size was distributed among the classes

according to the proportion of the students in each class relative to the total number of students in the school as follows:

$$\text{No of students to be sampled from a class} = \frac{\text{Total number of students in that class}}{\text{Total number of students in school}} \times 294$$

Total number of students in school

Students in each class were numbered consecutively starting from the number 1. This constituted the sampling frame for the study. Students to be studied were selected by simple random sampling using the ballot method.

Data was entered into IBM SPSS version 23 (SPSS Inc. IBM Corp. Chicago Illinois USA), double-checked and analysed. Descriptive statistics such as mean, median, percentages or proportions was used to present data from the sample. The number of correctly answered questions was used to determine the knowledge score. One point was scored for a correctly answered question and zero for a wrong answer. Overall scores was expressed in percentage (out of 25); an overall score of ≥ 19 points ($>75\%$) was considered as good knowledge, score of 13 to 18 points (50–75%) as fair knowledge and score ≤ 12 ($<50\%$) as poor knowledge. Frequency tables was used to present data. Comparisons between means was done using T-test and Chi-square test was used as measure of association between variables. *P*-values of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.⁸

Ethical Considerations: This study was conducted in accordance with the provisions of the Helsinki Declaration on research involving human subjects. Ethical approval was obtained from the Anambra state Ministry of Health Research and Ethics Committee (ASMOHREC/2024/14102024/22). Informed permission was sought from parents of the children and assent obtained from children aged 12 years and older in line with the National Policy on enrolment of children in research in Nigeria.

Permission was also obtained from the school. Confidentiality of participants' information was ensured.

RESULTS

A total of 296 students made up of 178 (60.1%) males and 118 (39.9%) females took part in this study. Mean age was 14.7 ± 1.3 and the ages ranged between 12 and 19 years (Table 1).

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics

Characteristic	No	%
Sex		
Male	178	60.1
Female	118	39.9
Class		
Junior secondary	150	50.7
Senior Secondary	146	49.3
Age (years)		
12	4	1.4
13	49	16.6
14	91	30.7
15	68	23.0
16	53	17.9
17	24	8.1
18	5	1.7
19	2	0.7

Before the educational intervention, the highest proportion of accurate responses was obtained for knowledge on taking an individual with red eyes to the hospital by 258(87.2%) of the respondents while the least accurate response was obtained for knowledge on measles as cause of blindness by 44 (14.9) (Table 2).

Table 2. Knowledge of eye health before educational intervention

Question	Correctly answered	
	Yes No (%)*	No No(%)*
Appropriate action in Chemical Eye Injury		
Olive oil	227 (76.7)	69 (23.3)
Onion	184 (62.2)	112 (37.8)
Blowing air into eye	175 (59.1)	21 (40.9)

Washing with water	219 (74.0)	77 (26.0)
Nothing just take to hospital	122 (41.2)	174 (58.8)
Appropriate action for stick injury		
Take to hospital	150 (50.7)	146 (49.3)
Pull stick out	98 (33.1)	198 (66.9)
Wash with water	134 (45.3)	162 (54.7)
Blow air into the eye	174 (58.8)	122 (41.2)
Use relative's old eye drop	201 (67.9)	95 (32.1)
Appropriate action for red eyes		
Urine instillation in the eye	130 (43.9)	166 (56.1)
Keep face and hands clean	160 (54.1)	136 (45.9)
Use relative's eye drop	181 (61.1)	115 (38.9)
Apply menthol ointment	222 (75.0)	74 (25.0)
Take to hospital	258 (87.2)	38 (12.8)
Causes of blindness		
Cataract	174 (58.8)	122 (41.2)
Diabetes	57 (19.3)	239 (80.7)
Measles	44 (14.9)	252(85.1)
Glaucoma	172(58.1)	124 (41.9)
Most common cause of blindness - cataract	103(34.8)	193 (65.2)
Spectacle and vision knowledge		
Glasses weaken the eyes	158 (53.4)	138 (46.6)
Children are too young for glasses	148 (50.0)	148 (50.0)
Eye check not necessary when there is no complaint	127 (42.9)	169 (57.1)
Eye problems can cause poor school performance	246 (83.1)	50 (16.9)
Most important vitamin for eye health	167 (56.4)	129 (43.6)

*% based on total of 296participants

Overall total knowledge score before educational intervention ranged between 2 and 23 out of 25 with a mean knowledge score of 13.67 ± 3.75 . The score of 13.67(54.7%) represents fair knowledge score. For the different segments assessed, out of a maximum attainable score of 5, the mean score for knowledge related to red eye was 3.21 ± 1.30 , chemical eye injury was 3.13 ± 1.30 , spectacle and vision was 2.86 ± 1.23 , stick injury was 2.56 ± 1.41 and causes of blindness was 1.86 ± 1.04 . Generally, 22 (7.4%) students had good eye health knowledge, 170 (57.4%) had fair knowledge while 104 (35.1%) had poor knowledge. Mean overall knowledge score for male students was 13.58 ± 3.80 while that for females was 13.78 ± 3.70 . There was no statistically significant difference between mean knowledge score by sex ($t = -0.438$; $p = 0.66$). There was a statistically significant difference in mean overall knowledge score between students in senior secondary and those in junior secondary school class with senior students having higher mean score (14.20 ± 3.73) than junior students, 13.14 ± 3.71 ($t = -2.448$); $p = 0.015$). Out of the 296 students who responded to the pre-educational intervention questionnaire, 238 (80.4%) responded to and returned the post-educational intervention questionnaire, a response rate of 80.4%. There was a statistically significant association between sex and study completion status of the students with more male students 43 (74.1%) not completing the study than females ($X^2 = 5.900$; $p = 0.015$) Also majority of those that did not complete the study were senior students, 47 (81.0%) ($X^2 = 29.019$, $p < 0.001$). The students who did not complete the post-test were 58(19.6%), representing approximately one-fifth of the sample population. A comparison of the pre-test scores of students who completed the pre-and post- tests with those who only completed the pre-test only is shown in table 3. There was no statistically significant difference in baseline knowledge between the two groups. ($t = -0.725$, $p = 0.469$).

Table 3. Overall pre- and post-test (completed) scores vs Pre-test (not completed) scores

Post-test completion Status	No	%	Mean overall pre-test score (SD)	T-test
Completed	238	80.4	13.58 (3.83)	t(294)
Not completed	58	19.6	13.98 (3.44)	=-
Total	296	100.0		0.725 p =0.469

The sociodemographic characteristics with completion status is shown in figure 4.

Table 4. Sociodemographic characteristics vs completion status

Characteristic	Study Completion Status		X2 (p-value)
	Complete No (%)	Pre-intervention only No (%)	
Sex			
Male	135 (56.7)	43 (74.1)	5.900 (0.015)
Female	103 (43.3)	15 (25.9)	
Total	238 (100.0)	58 (100.0)	
Class group			
Junior	139 (58.4)	11 (19.0)	29.019 (< 0.001)
Senior	99 (41.6)	47 (81.0)	
Total	238 (100.0)	58 (100.0)	

After educational intervention, the highest proportion of correct responses was for use of olive oil in chemical eye injury by 228 (95.8%) and the lowest was for knowledge of measles as a cause of blindness by 91 (38.2%). The eye health knowledge pre and post educational intervention is shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Knowledge before and after the Educational Intervention

Question	Correctly answered	
	Before No (%)*	After No (%)**
Appropriate action in Chemical Eye Injury		
Olive oil	227 (76.7)	228 (95.8)
Onion	184 (62.2)	222 (93.3)
Blowing air into eye	175 (59.1)	195 (81.9)
Washing with water	219 (74.0)	198 (83.2)

Nothing just take to hospital

Appropriate action for stick injury

Take to hospital 150 (50.7) 134 (56.3)
Pull stick out 98 (33.1) 102 (42.9)
Wash with water 134 (45.3) 116 (48.7)
Blow air into the eye 174 (58.8) 199 (83.6)
Use relative's old eye drop 201 (67.9) 219 (92.0)

Appropriate action for red eyes

Urine instillation in the eye 130 (43.9) 213 (89.5)
Keep face and hands clean 160 (54.1) 192 (80.7)
Use relative's eye drop 181 (61.1) 218 (91.6)
Apply menthol ointment 222 (75.0) 219 (92.0)
Take to hospital 258 (87.2) 217 (91.2)

Causes of blindness

Cataract 174 (58.8) 218 (91.6)
Diabetes 57 (19.3) 179 (75.2)
Measles 44 (14.9) 91 (38.2)
Glaucoma 172(58.1) 211 (88.7)
Most common cause of blindness - cataract 101(34.8) 120 (50.4)

Spectacle and vision knowledge

Glasses weaken the eyes 158 (53.4) 195 (81.9)
Children are too young for glasses 148 (50.0) 201 (84.5)
Eye check not necessary when there is no complaint 127 (42.9) 143 (60.1)
Eye problems can cause poor school performance 248 (83.1) 219 (92.0)
Most important vitamin for eye health 167 (56.4) 205 (86.1)

*% based on 296. **% based on 238

The overall mean total knowledge score after the educational intervention was 19.33 ± 3.38 ; range was 6 to 25. The post-intervention score represents good knowledge, 19.33(77.3%). The difference in overall mean knowledge scores between pre and post educational intervention ranged from -8 to 20.

The largest change in knowledge score was observed for causes of blindness, while the least change was on questions related to stick injury. There was a statistically significant difference in mean knowledge score between pre-educational intervention knowledge scores and post educational intervention knowledge scores with post-intervention mean knowledge scores being higher overall and for the different areas assessed ($p=0.001$) (Table 6).

Table 6. Comparison of mean knowledge scores before and after educational intervention

Knowledge area	Mean before	Mean after	Difference in mean	t df (p-value)
Chemical eye injury	3.10	4.20	1.10	11.02237 (<0.001)
Stick injury	2.55	3.22	0.67	6.00237 (<0.001)
Red eye	3.20	4.42	1.22	11.96237 (<0.001)
Causes of blindness	1.85	3.43	1.58	18.20237 (<0.001)
Spectacle and vision	2.86	4.05	1.19	11.73237 (<0.001)
Overall	13.67	19.33	5.75	19.30237 (<0.001)

Students in junior secondary school had a statistically significant higher mean change in knowledge score (6.35 ± 4.82) than those in senior secondary school, 4.91 ± 4.14 . ($t = 2.46$; $p = 0.015$). No statistically significant difference in mean change in knowledge score was found between males, 5.84 ± 4.64 and females, 5.62 ± 4.56 ($t = 0.370$, $p = 0.599$).

DISCUSSION

The results of this study showed that on the average, there is a fair knowledge (54.7%) of eye health among the students studied. This improved to good knowledge level (77.3%)

following the eye health education activity. Eye health education increases the awareness and knowledge of healthy eye behaviours and good eye practices among the recipients. The learned good eye practices are of immense benefits to students who are still in their formative years. It is easier to unlearn bad practices and imbibe good eye health knowledge that will carry the student throughout life. A study in Nepal similarly reported a significant improvement in knowledge of eye health among students of a Government secondary school following an eye health education intervention.⁵ Baseline knowledge in our study (54.7%) was higher than was reported in the Nepal study(44%).⁵

In this study, pre-intervention results showed that more than half of the students had fair knowledge on eye health knowledge and also knew the common causes of blindness as cataract and glaucoma. However, in a study conducted more than two decades ago in a rural area in the same state among adults aged 20 years and above had approximately 30% having post primary education where the causes of blindness were attributed to filariasis, germs and enemy poison.¹⁰ While this study was carried in an urban area in a school within one kilometre from an eye hospital, it may be necessary to replicate similar study in a rural secondary school to ascertain influences of location on eye health knowledge.

A study done in Kano Nigeria by Abubalkar and Jibo, among secondary school students showed that only 20% had good knowledge on causes of blindness.¹¹ In this study, being in senior secondary class was significantly associated with more health knowledge while gender has no influence. This was similarly reported by Karn *et al.* in Nepal.⁵ However, in the study at Kano, female gender and being in senior classes were significantly associated with more knowledge.¹¹ A study done among secondary school students in Enugu Nigeria showed that those in senior classes compared to junior classes had listened to previous eye health talks.¹² It is possible that as

one matures, interest in things thought outside school curriculum may increase and account for more eye health knowledge among senior class students.

In the pre-educational intervention assessment on red eyes/conjunctivitis, 87.2% knew that the patient should be taken to the hospital. However, responses in support of the instillation of urine, menthol ointment and use of relatives' old eye drops were quite high, accounting for at least one quarter of responses. This was reduced to about 1 in 10 following the educational intervention (Table 5). This highlights a need for sustained education of school students on appropriate eye care practices. Such continuous education will help provide them with correct information and orientation about the dangers of the use of harmful traditional eye medications which could in turn help reduce the use of traditional eye medications. This is especially important considering the high prevalence of traditional eye medication use and attendant visual impairment and blindness.¹³ Similar to our study findings, a study among secondary school students in Sagamu, Nigeria reported that majority of the students knew the doctor takes care of red eyes but they would also subscribe to the use of onions, urine and breast milk to treat red eyes.¹⁴

In the pre-health education assessment, half of the students who participated felt that children did not need to wear glasses, though majority of participating students agree that eye problems affect school performance. The opinion on discouraging students from wearing glasses may be a reflection of societal views. Children tend to believe the practices and opinions of adults including their parents' whether it is evidence-based or not. A study in South East, Nigeria on adults' perception on use of spectacle showed that a significant minority considers use of spectacle as harmful practice because children are still in their formative years.¹⁵ Concerning knowledge of

vitamin A as an important vitamin for eye health, students in an Indian study of eye health knowledge among secondary school students (79.1%) fared better than those in our current study (56.4%).¹⁶ This may be due to differences in information that students in the different populations are exposed to.

The sources of eye health knowledge varies but one from trained personnel is usually superior and accurate. The health talk as an intervention was done by an experienced ophthalmologist. It is necessary to train other cadres of health workers as well as teachers to carry out eye health education with demonstrations so that no secondary school student is left behind. A scoping review of knowledge and attitude of teachers towards school children's eye health revealed that low to moderate knowledge with some persisting misconceptions.¹⁷ It is important to assess teachers' eye health knowledge and also get them adequately trained to equip them to carry out their roles in the eye health education of children.

The results show a significant increase in eye health knowledge among the students. The findings from the study, show the benefit of well-planned eye health education to correct the misconceptions of secondary school students who are in their formative years. It was however observed that despite the educational intervention, less than two-thirds of the students exhibited accurate knowledge related to taking a person with chemical eye injury to the hospital without first aid, taking a person with stick injury to the hospital first, attempting to pull out a stick in the eye, washing eye with stick injury with water, knowledge of measles as cause of blindness, the most common cause of blindness in Nigeria and the necessity of going for eye check even in the absence of eye complaint (Table 5). This could be because the intervention was one time and utilised mostly talks and poster as means of education. On the contrary, a study of students

in Nepal reported that knowledge of-most common cause of blindness which is cataract improved up to 83%.⁵ This study, though had a one-time intervention utilised multiple education methods like brainstorming, lecture methods, demonstration, video shows, role play, poster presentation and PowerPoint unlike in our study where only lecture method and poster presentation were used. It is likely that a more frequent, multi-pronged approach to eye health education of students employing different methods of education could be more beneficial in improving retention of eye health information and thereby further increasing its effectiveness. This is supported by a study in Korea among middle school students which reported improvement in eye health-related knowledge using multiple educational methods in four weekly sessions.¹⁸

In this study, more males and senior students didn't take the post-health intervention assessment. This study did not set out to find out reasons for non-participation of these students. However as eye health knowledge is planned, it is important to ensure that each child benefits maximally and is able to transfer the knowledge acquired to practical situations. The material used for the health education of the students was that approved for primary schools. We suggest that emphasis should also be placed on the eye health education of primary school pupils to make sure eye health knowledge gap is filled before they get to the secondary school where further reinforcement of their eye health knowledge should take place.

The strength of this study lies in the large sample size and the ability of the study design to measure the effectiveness of our educational intervention. Also, the post-educational questionnaire was administered immediately to avoid attrition though some students still dropped out. However the regression effect that occurs when the same questionnaire is used twice cannot be overruled.

It is also possible that with time the efficacy of our educational intervention on the students may decrease. Another limitation of our study was the non-validated research instrument used. However, our intervention provided health education to all students and our questionnaire was able to offer insight into students' eye health knowledge.

CONCLUSION

Eye Health Knowledge was fair among these secondary school students and improved to good knowledge after an eye health educational intervention. Thus, eye health education is effective in improving eye health knowledge of students. We recommend continuous eye health education for secondary school students. This could be achieved by means of lectures, posters, audio-visual displays, role plays and demonstrations.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate: Ethical approval was obtained from the Anambra state Ministry of Health Research and Ethics Committee (ASMOHREC/2024/14102024/22). Informed permission was sought from parents of the children and assent obtained from children aged 12 years and older in line with the National Policy on enrolment of children in research in Nigeria. Permission was also obtained from the school.

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Competing interest: None.

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